

Reactions of Stannic alkoxides with Glycols

R. C. Mehrotra and V. D. Gupta

A number of di-isopropoxy mono-glycolate and diglycolate derivatives of tin have been described for the first time by the reaction between stannic isopropoxide and various glycols in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios. A few mixed ethylene glycolates have also been isolated. With a view to synthesizing some volatile derivatives the reactions of monomeric stannic tertiary butoxide with some of these branched glycols were also investigated. The determination of molecular weights showed them to be polymeric.

In view of the interesting properties obtained in the study of the glycol derivatives of B¹,² Al³, Si⁴, Ge⁵, Ti⁶, Nb⁷, Ta⁸, Se⁹ and Te⁹, it was considered worth while to investigate similar reactions of the stannic alkoxides. Moreover, a perusal of the literature gives no evidence for the synthesis of similar products. The isolation of these glycol derivatives has been accomplished by the alcohol interchange of alkoxides and the progress of the reaction was followed by the estimation of the liberated alcohol in the azeotrope. This appears to be the only possible method for the synthesis of such compounds.

The reaction of stannic isopropoxide, Sn (OC₃H₇)₄. C₃H₇OH, with various glycols (ethylene glycol, propane 1, 2 diol, propane 1,3 diol, 3-chloropropane 1,2 diol, 1,3—1,4—2,3 butane diols, 1,5 pentane diol, 1,6—hexane diol, hexylene glycol and pinacol) in 1:1 molar ratios yielded di-isopropoxy monoglycolates which can be represented by the equation:

The ethylene glycolate derivative was found to be sparingly soluble in benzene and the di-isopropoxy compounds of 1,5—pentane and 1,6—hexane diols were almost insoluble. Except these, all other derivatives are generally soluble, the hexylene and pinacol derivatives showing extraordinarily high solubility, characteristic of their derivatives with other metals also. Attempts to volatilise the hexylene glycol and pinacol derivatives of tin (IV) were not successful.

The reactions of stannic isopropoxide with all the above glycols, in 1:2 molar ratios, yielded the bisderivatives (as shown by equation 1) quantitatively except in the case of

1. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1032, 3810.
2. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 203.
3. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 636.
4. Mehrotra and Pant, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 563.
5. Mehrotra and Chandra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2804.
6. Puri, *Ph.D. Thesis*, Gorakhpur University, 1962.
7. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *J. Less-common Metals*, 1965, 8, 419.
8. Mehrotra and Kapoor, *ibid.* (in Press).
9. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this Journal*, 1963, 42, 749, 814.

1,5—pentane and 1,6—hexane diols (equation 2) where the replacement of the fourth iso-propoxy group could not be effected:

As most of the di-isopropoxy glycolate derivatives could neither be crystallised nor volatilised, the identity of these products requires some further consideration as they might be considered to be equimolecular mixtures of stannic diglycolates and the unchanged stannic isopropoxide. The insolubility of the diglycolates derived from ethylene glycol, 3-chloropropane 1,2 diol, 1,4—1,3—butane diols, 1,5—pentane diol, and 1,6—hexane diol in benzene ruled out this possibility as their di-isopropoxy monoglycolate derivatives are soluble in this solvent. In order to substantiate the identity of the di-isopropoxy monoglycolates in the cases of propane 1,2 diol, propane 1,3 diol, 2,3 butane diol, hexylene glycol and pinacol, they were treated with ethylene glycol in 1:1 molar ratios. If the initial material were an equimolar mixture of stannic isopropoxide and diglycolate these reactions with ethylene glycol could be represented by the following equation and would have yielded insoluble stannic bis (ethylene glycolates):

However, the formation of a soluble derivative corresponding in analysis to $\text{Sn}(\text{gl})(\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ in all cases except in the case of propane 1,3—diol indicated that the reaction can be represented by the following equation and also confirmed the identity of the di-isopropoxy glycolate derivatives:

It has been observed in the case of germanium⁵ that the thermal stability of analogous compounds increases with steric hindrance and thus the corresponding derivatives of pinacol (2,3-dimethyl, butane 2,3-diol) and hexylene glycol (2-methyl pentane 2,4 diol) could be distilled unchanged. In view of this the reaction of these glycols were carried out with the monomeric stannic tertiary butoxide. Both the derivatives, $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O})_n \text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2$ were found to be highly soluble in benzene. The former compound disproportionated into stannic tertiary butoxide and the diglycolate on being heated under reduced pressure whereas the pinacol derivative could be sublimed unchanged. This can be explained to be due to the presence of two tertiary carbon atoms which offers greater

steric restrictions. The molecular weight determination of this pinacollate derivative in benzene shows it to be essentially dimeric.

The striking variation in the solubility of various glycolates listed in the table can be correlated either to their tendency of chelation (A) or to the formation of high polymeric units (B):

The insolubility of mono- as well as the di-derivatives of ethylene glycol might be ascribed to the formation of sterically favoured five membered ring (A). The methyl groups on the α -carbon atoms in propane 1,2-diol, butane 2,3 diol might cause some hindrance to a packed ring formation of the type A and may partially lead to a chain structure of the type B. As the number of carbon atoms in the glycol chain itself increases, the tendency of chelation would show a marked decrease due to the comparative instability of larger rings and hence the polymerisation of the type B may be fairly extensive in glycols of the type pentane 1,5- or hexane 1,6-diols making both mono- as well as di-derivatives insoluble. Although the above explanations are speculative only in the absence of any structural information on these derivatives, yet they appear to be qualitatively in general accord with most of the properties enumerated in the table.

TABLE I

Reactants (g)	Nature of the product (g)	Analysis									
		Alcohol		g		Sn%		Glycoxy%		Molecular Weight	
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
R, ethylene glycol benzene	(2.82) (0.421) (68)	Sn(O ₂ C ₂ H ₅) ₂ (O ₂ C ₂ H ₄)	1.19	1.22	41.6	39.9	21.2	20.9	—	—	—
R, ethylene glycol benzene	(3.68) (1.1) (70)	Sn(O ₂ C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Insoluble white solid (2.0)	2.62	2.66	48.9	49.7	50.8	50.3	—	—	—
R, propane 1,2-diol benzene	(4.2) (0.77) (71)	Sn(O ₂ C ₃ H ₇) ₂ (O ₂ C ₃ H ₆)	1.76	1.82	39.1	38.2	24.0	23.8	1280	3109	—
R, propane 1,2-diol benzene	(4.23) (1.55) (68)	Sn(O ₂ C ₃ H ₇) ₂ White solid moderately soluble in benzene (2.6)	2.95	3.06	43.5	44.4	55.1	55.8	1014	266.8	—

R = Sn(O₂C₃H₇)₂·CH₂OH

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TABLE I (Contd.)

Reactants	Nature of products (g)	A n a l y s i s						Molecular Weight	
		Alcohol (g)		Sn%		glycoxy%			
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
R, (4.35)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$) White solid slightly soluble in benzene (3.4)	1.79	1.88	35.8	35.0	—	—	—	—
pentane 1,5-diol benzene (48)									
R, (2.33)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$) ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$) Insoluble white solid (2.1)	1.32	1.34	30.5	30.9	—	—	—	—
pentane 1,5-diol benzene (68)									
R, (3.01)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) White solid slightly soluble in benzene (2.3)	1.27	1.30	34.0	33.6	—	—	—	—
hexane 1,6-diol benzene (67)									
R, (2.03)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) Insoluble white solid (1.94)	1.15	1.17	28.6	28.8	—	—	—	—
hexane 1,6-diol benzene (67)									
R, (4.21)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) Viscous liquid (3.5)	1.80	1.82	33.4	33.6	—	—	1266	353
hexylene glycol benzene (64)									
R, (4.43)	$\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12})_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) Soluble white solid (3.7)	3.08	3.20	33.2	33.8	—	—	1120	351
hexylene glycol benzene (49)									
R, (3.96)	$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) White solid soluble in benzene (3.3)	1.68	1.71	34.0	33.6	31.6	32.9	979	353
pinacol benzene (68.5)									
R, [R= pinacol benzene (68)] (2.14) (1.21) (68)	$\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12})_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$) Soluble white solid (1.65)	1.50	1.54	33.5	33.8	66.0	66.2	1106	351
B', (propane 1,2-diol ethylene glycol benzene (49.5)) (1.01) (0.202) (49.5)	$\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$) White solid slightly soluble in benzene (0.81)	0.95	0.99	47.1	47.0	—	—	—	—
R', (propane 1,3-diol ethylene glycol benzene (61)) (1.11) (0.218) (61)	$\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ ($\text{O}_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7$) Insoluble white solid (0.85)	0.38	0.42	46.5	47.0	—	—	—	—

TABLE I (contd.)

Reactants	Nature of products (g)	Analysis							
		Alcohol (g)		Sn%		glyoxy%		Molecular Weight	
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
R', (butane 2,3- diol ethylene glycol (0.271) benzene (60)	(1.42) $\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) soluble brown solid (1.15)	0.49	0.52	44.1	44.4	—	—	849	266.8
R', hexylene glycol ethylene glycol (0.316) benzene (59)	(1.79) $\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$) Yellow solid soluble in benzene (1.42)	0.57	0.61	39.7	40.2	—	—	770	294.9
R', (pinacol) ethylene glycol (0.474) benzene (61)	(2.7) $\text{Sn}(\text{O}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2$ ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$) Soluble yellow solid (2.22)	0.84	0.91	39.8	40.2	—	—	777	294.9
R', hexylene glycol (1.39) benzene (68)	(4.83) $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$)* Pale viscous liquid soluble in benzene (4.4)	—	—	31.6	31.1	—	—	—	—
R', pinacol benzene (63)	(7.23) $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$) White solid soluble in benzene. Sub- limed at a bath temp. of 150-170°C under 0.1 mm pressure. (5.2)	—	—	31.1	31.1	32.0	30.4	850	381

*In spite of fairly high solubility, the molecular weight could not be determined in these cases due to the practical difficulty of handling these products.

EXPERIMENTAL

All glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout this work and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

The glycols employed were distilled twice before use. Stannic tertiary butoxide and isopropoxide were prepared as reported earlier^{10,11}

10. Mehrotra and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 537

11. Mehrotra and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1966, 43, 155 (In Press.)

Glyoxy contents were estimated¹², by Malaprade method¹³ with sodium periodate. Butane 1,4-diol was estimated with normal chromic acid; as the reaction did not proceed to completion, a blank experiment was always performed. The estimation of pinacol required quantitatively two equivalents of the oxidant when carried out with normal chromic acid.

Other experimental details and analytical procedures have been described before^{10,11,14}. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) with thermister sensing in benzene, providing an accuracy of about $\pm 1\%$ for ordinary organic compounds. In view of the hydrolysable nature of the alkoxy tin derivatives, the accuracy is slightly less but generally well within the range of $\pm 5\%$.

Reaction between stannic isopropoxide and glycol: To a benzene solution of stannic isopropoxide was added a calculated amount of glycol. The solution was refluxed (bath temperature 110-120°C) followed by fractionation of the isopropanol-benzene azeotrope between 72-80°C. Excess solvent was distilled out and the product was dried under reduced pressure (0.1-1.0 mm) at the room temperature (28-36°C). The various results have been tabulated.

Reaction between stannic tertiary butoxide and hexylene glycol (molar ratio 1:1): Stannic tertiary butoxide (4.83g) was admitted into benzene (68g) containing hexylene glycol (1.39g) and was refluxed. After fractionating out the azeotrope of butanolbenzene and excess solvent, a pale viscous liquid (4.4g) was obtained when the product was dried under reduced pressure. Found: Sn, 31.6%. Calc. for Sn $(OC_4H_9)_2(O_2C_6H_{12})_2$: Sn, 31.1%. The compound (1.6g) disproportionated when heated under reduced pressure. A colourless liquid (0.8g) was distilled at 68-69°C/0.6. mm and a light yellow residue (0.7g) was left in the flask.

Distillate—Found: Sn, 29.1%. Calc. for Sn $(OC_4H_9)_4$: Sn, 28.8%.

Residue: Found: Sn, 34.8%. Calc. for Sn $(O_2C_6H_{12})_2$: Sn, 33.8%.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
JAIPUR, INDIA.

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12. Gupta, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University (Jaipur), 1965.

13. Malaprade, Bull. Soc. Chim., France, 1928, 43, 683.

14. Mehrotra and Gupta, this Journal, 1963, 40, 911.